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Confirmation of the presence of recently described *Dorcadion fulvum* ssp. *opillicum* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in Poland

A. M. Zamoroka ^{1*}, T. Olbrycht ²¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5692-7997>² <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2854-4467>¹ Department of Biology and Ecology Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Shevchenko, 57, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine, 76018² Department of Agroecology and Forest Utilization, University of Rzeszów, ul. M. Ćwiklińskiej 1, 35-601 Rzeszów, Poland

* Corresponding author

E-mail: andrew.zamoroka@pnu.edu.ua

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Zamoroka, A. M. & Olbrycht, T. — The recently described subspecies of *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum* Zamoroka, 2019 was known from a limited range within the westernmost part of Podillya Upland. However, it was hypothesized that it is more widespread and likely occupies South-Eastern Poland. In the current study, we solved the puzzle of the subspecies of *Dorcadion fulvum*. Our findings clearly show that the specimens from South-Eastern Poland belong to *D. f. opillicum*. Provided data dramatically expand the originally known borders of its distribution including Roztocze, Lublin and Volyn' Uplands.

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, long-horned beetles, *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum*, Poland, Ukraine.

Підтвердження присутності нещодавно описаного *Dorcadion fulvum* ssp. *opillicum* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) у Польщі.

Заморока, А.М. і Ольбрихт, Т. — Нещодавно описаний підвид *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum* Zamoroka, 2019 до сьогодні був відомим лише із невеликого регіону на заході Подільської височини в Україні. Проте, раніше висловлювалось припущення, що його ареал повинен бути значно ширшим і ймовірно охоплює південно-західну Польщу. У чинній публікації ми вперше дослідили зразки *Dorcadion fulvum* (Scopoli, 1763) із Польщі на предмет їхньої підвидової приналежності. Отримані результати підтверджують припущення про поширення *D. f. opillicum* у цьому регіоні, що значною мірою розширило уявлення про його відомий ареал на територію Розточчя, Люблінської та Волинської височин.

Ключові слова: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, жуки-вусачі, *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum*, Польща, Україна.

Introduction

Dorcadion fulvum (Scopoli, 1763) is a Ponto-Pannonic species widespread within Pannonic basin, north of Balkans and Ukrainian uplands as far as Dnipro River on the east. The species is subdivided into four subspecies: *Dorcadion fulvum fulvum* (Scopoli, 1763), *Dorcadion fulvum cervae* Frivaldsky, 1892, *Dorcadion fulvum erythropterum* Fischer von Waldheim, 1823 and *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum* Zamoroka, 2019 (Zamoroka, 2019). In Poland, *D. fulvum* occurs on the northernmost margin of its natural range. However, its distribution was poorly known here, because of deficient of comprehensive scientific both collected and published data. Since the late XIX century, it is known that natural range of *D. fulvum* consists of western

and eastern parts in Poland (Gerhardt, 1891; Kuntze and Noskiewicz, 1938). These parts are isolated from each other and separated by large territories of Podkarpacie. This disjunction was once pointed out by R. Kuntze and J. Noskiewicz (1938), emphasizing zoogeographic features of the species in Poland and Western Ukraine.

In the western part of the range, *D. fulvum* is known from the vicinities of Raciborz and Cieszyn, based on the very old report (Gerhardt, 1891). This data periodically repeated in many later sources (Kuntze and Noskiewicz, 1938; Burakowski 1957; Burakowski et al., 1989; Zamoroka, 2019). However, there were no recent confirmation of these data. Burakowski et al. (1989) assumed that the western part of *D. fulvum* range likely

represents the nominative subspecies *D. f. fulvum*. Their suggestion needs confirmation using a new data collected.

The eastern part of *D. fulvum* range occupies Roztocze and Lublin Upland in Poland. Hildt (1917) defined that the species spreads to the southeast of the interfluvium of Wisła and Wieprz. He noticed that *D. fulvum* is rare and spreads very locally and sporadically within xerophilous habitats. Kuntze & Noskiewicz (1938) found *D. fulvum* in vicinity of Zamość. Later, Burakowski (1957) confirmed their findings. He collected a single elytron of *D. fulvum* near Klemensów west of Zamość. By the end of the XX century there were no further records of *D. fulvum* in Poland. There were some speculations that the species was extinct in the region. However, by the end of the last century, *D. fulvum* was recorded from Roztocze near Machnów, Tomaszów Lubelski County (Gutowski et al. 1999). Recently, this species occurred in the vicinity of Perespa (Tomaszów Lubelski County) due to the citizen science observation (iNaturalist, 2020). Finally, our current record of *D. fulvum* from surroundings of Gródek, Hrubieszów County expands its known range northward in Poland.

Until recently, it was believed that *D. fulvum* belongs to the subspecies *D. f. erythropterum* in South-Eastern Poland (Burakowski and al., 1989; Mapa..., 2021). This subspecies is widespread on Balkans and in Ukraine (Zamoroka, 2019). However, this assertion has been questioned due to the recent description of a new subspecies *D. f. opillicum* from Western Ukraine (Zamoroka, 2019). Zamoroka (2019) hypothesized, that South-Eastern Polish *D. fulvum* belongs to *D. f. opillicum*. However, he has not examined specimens from Poland and the question of the taxonomic position of local *Dorcadion fulvum* remained open until now.

In this study, we examined specimens of *D. fulvum* collected in Eastern Poland and proven their belonging to the recently described subspecies of *D. f. opillicum*. This is the first confirmation of its presence in Poland. Our findings

dramatically expanded the originally known borders of its range including Roztocze, Lublin and Volyn' Uplands.

Methods

Depository abbreviation: PUIF – Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, entomological collection.

Insects were observed on the surface of soil. One naturally dead male was taken for laboratory study. It was dissected and its genitalia were studied and compared with those of holotype deposited in PUIF. For this purpose, we used a Nikon SMZ-1 stereomicroscope at 40× magnification. Photographs were taken using a DLTCam PRO 5 MP USB camera attached to the stereomicroscope. The habitus photographs of the entire beetle were taken using Nikon D90 camera. Images were then aligned and stacked in the DLTCamViewer x86, 3.7.7892 software package and enhanced in Adobe Photoshop CS3 v. 10.0.

Results and discussion

Dorcadion fulvum opillicum Zamoroka, 2019

Material. Type. Holotype ♂: Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Kuropatnyky, 49.286027 N, 24.669622 E, 19.06.2015 (Zamoroka) (PUIF). Paratype: 1♀, same labels as in holotype (PUIF). **Non-type.** Poland: Lublin Upland, UTM GB03, Gródek, Hrubieszów County, 50.795858 N, 23.957577 E (fig. 1A), 3♂, 2♀ 01.05.2009 (obs. T. Olbrycht). One specimen is deposited in PUIF.

Our record of *Dorcadion fulvum* is one of the few recent findings of this species in Poland. This refutes the assumption of the possible extinction of this species here. On the other hand, this proves an idea that *D. fulvum* is widespread within Roztocze and Lublin Upland. However, its range is not continuous, but represents a number of isolated islands. Our observations in Nadbużański Obszar Chronionego Krajobrazu and the Natura 2000 site

Fig.1. Habitat of *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum* in the vicinity of Gródek, Hrubieszów County (A) and live beetles in the wild (B and C).

“Zachodniowołyńska Dolina Bugu” (PLH 060035) showed that the most typical habitats for *D. fulvum* are xerothermic *Thalictro-Salvietum pratensis* complex grasslands on the southern steep slopes of the hills along the Bug River (fig. 1A). Very rarely, *D. fulvum* occurs on arable lands or other agricultural or seminatural areas. It should be emphasised that the observed habitat differs from those in *D. f. opillicum* type locality. This includes other types of vegetation (*Brachypodietalia pinnati* and *Festucetalia valesiaca*) and soil composition (contained amount of crushed gypsum debris) within type locality (Zamoroka, 2019).

Comparison of *Dorcadion fulvum* samples from the vicinity of Gródek, Hrubieszów County with both subspecies of *D. f. erythropterum* and *D. f. opillicum* shows general morphological resemblance to the latter. First of all, this includes more or less dark integument coloration, especially of elytra. In addition to the common dark forms

(fig. 1B) at the studied site there are specimens of partially dark colour (Fig. 2, B) or completely light (fig. 1C), which resemble *D. f. erythropterum*. In a type series of *D. f. opillicum* light-coloured specimens constitute about 27% (Zamoroka, 2019). Secondly, elytra of studied specimens are roughly sculpted with a well-developed humeral rib (especially in females) similar to *D. f. opillicum*. Elytra of males and females are more or less dimmed by dense coarse punctation and wrinkling. Contrary to them, the elytra sculpture of *D. f. erythropterum* is significantly smoothed with a clear sheen, without a distinct rough punctation. Finally, the elongated labrum and convex occiput are inherited in *Dorcadion fulvum* from the vicinity of Gródek. These features are typical for *D. f. opillicum*.

The aedeagi of both *D. fulvum* from Gródek and *D. f. opillicum* are almost identical, sharing the shape

Fig. 2. Comparison of *D. fulvum* from the vicinity of Gródek, Hrubieszów County (B; E) with the holotype of *D. fulvum opillicum* (A, D, from Zamoroka, 2019), and *D. fulvum erythropterum* (Berezivka, Odesa Region) (C, F, from Zamoroka, 2019).

and proportions of proximal and distal parts (Fig. 3). In particular, their ventral and dorsal lobes are big and long, contrary to those in *D. f. erythropterum*. The ratio of proximal and distal parts of aedeagus constitutes near 1:1 (fig. 3D–E), which is different from that ratio in *D. f. erythropterum* (Fig. 3F). These clearly indicate that *D. fulvum* from Gródek belongs to the recently described subspecies *D. f. opillicum*. It should be noted that the aedeagus apex of *D. fulvum* from Gródek (fig. 3B) is less sclerotized and less deeply truncated than in the holotype of *D. f. opillicum* (fig. 3A).

Dorcadion fulvum from Gródek and *D. f. opillicum* also share morphological features of the tegmens (fig. 4). Their parameres are elongate, punctated on internal side and covered by short pubescence from their base to the apex. The tegmal ring of *D. fulvum* from Gródek is relatively short and near the same length that parameres, which is similar to *D. f. opillicum*, whereas in *D. f. erythropterum* (fig. 4C, F) the parameres are short and the tegmal ring is strongly elongated.

Our data convincingly indicate that *D. fulvum* from South-Eastern Poland belong to the recently described subspecies *D. f. opillicum*. This is evidenced by both the similarity of external morphology and the structure of the male genitalia. Our findings also have biogeographical implications as they extend the known range of *D. f. opillicum* west to the Wisła and north to Polissya (fig. 5). However, the eastern boundaries of its range and the location of the introgression zone between *D. f. opillicum* and *D. f. erythropterum* still remain unresolved.

Comparative material

Dorcadion fulvum erythropterum Fischer von Waldheim, 1823

Material examined. Ukraine: Odesa: Berezivka, 47.206298 N, 30.932801 E, 09.05.2010, 1♂, 1♀ (Kravchenko) (PUIF).

Fig. 3. Comparison of dorsal (A–C) and lateral (D–F) view of the male aedeagi of *D. fulvum* from the vicinity of Gródek, Hrubieszów County (B; E) with holotype of *D. fulvum opillicum* (A, D, from Zamoroka, 2019), and *D. fulvum erythropterum* (Berezivka, Odesa Reg.) (C, F, from Zamoroka, 2019).

Fig.4. Comparison of dorsal (A-C) and lateral (D-F) view of the male tegmens of *D. fulvum* from the vicinity of Gródek, Hrubieszów County (B; E) with holotype of *D. fulvum opillicum* (A, D, from Zamoroka, 2019), and *D. fulvum erythropterum* (Berezivka, Odesa Region) (C, F, from Zamoroka, 2019).

Fig.5. The suggested range of *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum* in Poland and Ukraine. Distribution of *Dorcadion fulvum erythropterum* (after Zamoroka, 2019) and *Dorcadion fulvum fulvum* (after Slama, 1998) is shown.

Conclusion

The puzzle of the subspecies of *Dorcadion fulvum* in SE Poland has been solved. Our findings clearly show that it belongs to the recently described subspecies *D. fulvum opillicum*. The provided data dramatically expanded originally known borders of its range including Roztocze, Lublin and Volyn' Uplands.

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